

SHAPED FABRICS FOR REINFORCEMENT OF AXI-SYMMETRIC SHELL STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

An automatic loom for weaving a shaped preform for shell structures has been developed. The fabrics, this loom can provide, are composed of radial and circumferential fibers and one of purposes of the loom is to provide preforms for a composite of revolutionary shell structures especially required high dimensional stability. To clarify advantages of the shaped fabrics, thermo-mechanical properties and behavior of the composite made of the fabric were compared with a composite made by conventional procedure using the plane cloth. It was shown by the comparison that the composite with shaped fabrics exhibited exceptional thermo-mechanical stability.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber composites have been extensively used in various fields due to their high performance. Their usage is however restricted to parts with relatively simple geometry. If we dare to make composites with a complex shape unwillingly straining prepreg, the degradation of composite properties will result from fiber fracture and/or perturbation of fiber orientation. Thus to provide the continuous fiber composites with a complex shape maintaining high performance, it becomes pivotal work to develop a preform already having the final shape required for the structure¹⁾. The purpose of the loom newly developed and to be presented here is to provide such preforms for arbitrary axi-symmetric shell structures. Main focus of the paper will be placed upon demonstration of superiority of the composite reinforced by the shaped fabrics through the comparison of performance with the composites reinforced by the conventional plane fabrics when they are used for antenna reflector with the shape of a spherical surface that is required high thermo-mechanical stability^{2),3),4)}.

WEAVING OF SHAPED FABRICS

Mechanism of the newly developed automatic loom for axisymmetrically shaped fabrics is schematically shown in Fig.1. Main motion of the loom is composed of exchange of the shuttle between the upper and lower tables and rotational movement of the bobbin around the center axis of the loom. These movements yield switching of the radial fibers between the upper and lower table positions as well as insertion of circumferential fiber. Thus the fabric was weaved on the surface of the mold. To render the fabrics form into the same shape as the mold surface, the mold was intermittently rising during the weaving motion. The typical shapes of the fabrics this loom can provide are surface of rotational body such as a conical surface,

circular tube, flange as well as spherical surface shown in Fig.2(a). The loom can weave two kinds of fiber constructions. One of the micro structures is conventional plane weave shown in Fig.2(a). Another is tri-axial weave shown in Fig.2(b), wherein typical fiber orientation angle are 0° and $\pm 60^\circ$ that is the same orientation constitution as Barbar Coleman's⁴⁾ and the composites using this fabric exhibits in-plane isotropy of elastic moduli. To weave the tri-axial fabric, rotation of the upper table around center axis of the loom was needed in addition to the before-mentioned motion of the loom.

SHAPING OF PLANE FABRIC

In order to clarify advantages of the use of the shaped fabrics, thermo-mechanical properties of a shaped fabric composite will be compared with a conventional composite composed of the plane fabric of the plane weave. Thus next let us consider the shaping of the plane fabric into sphericity shown in Fig.3(a). The shaping was assumed to be done with the lines of $\varphi=0^\circ$ and 90° (X and Y axes) of the fabric shown in Fig.4 at first fixed to the surface of sphere (longitude OA and OB). It should be noted in the Fig.3 (a) that the intersection angle χ of the fibers in the fabric deviates from original 90° to smaller angle with the change of the shape from the plane to the sphericity. The variation of χ can be analytically predicted by the method of Robertson et.al.⁵⁾ and one of the results is shown in Fig.5 where angles, θ and φ , are defined in Fig.4 and M denotes number of unit cells for the plane cloth within the distance from the pole (point O) of the sphere to the equator (curve A-B) and $\varphi=45^\circ$ is the line on which the maximum change of occurs. As is obvious from the figure, reduction of χ increases with the distance from the pole and χ reaches at about 37° in the vicinity of the equator. This change of fiber orientation induces locational variation of the fiber density as well as anisotropic material properties.

On the contrary, the shaped fabrics can be precisely controlled fiber orientation and fiber density. Fig.6 (a) and (b) show typical examples of the fiber density design of a shaped fabric made of 6K graphite fiber. The vertical axes of the figures L_s and L_r denote interval of the neighboring circumferential and radial fiber bundle, respectively, and the horizontal axis r the distance from the pole of the sphericity for the case of the radius of the sphere equal to 200mm. As is obvious from the weaving procedure, the fiber density is axi-symmetric in the shaped fabric. In the two kinds of fibers, the density of the radial fiber is geometrically determined by the number of the bundles. Thus to unify the radial fiber density, new fiber bundle was proportionally added with continuous increase of fabric diameter during weaving process. In Fig. 6, the addition of the bundle was suggested at the point of abrupt increase and decrease of L_s and L_r , respectively. The frequency of the bundle addition was denoted by N_f , that is, $N_f=1$ and $N_f=3$ stand for that the bundle addition was done in every 1 and 3 insertion of the circumferential bundle. For the case of $N_f=1$, the density design curve fractuates intensively. Thus only envelope of the curve is shown by the dotted line for this case.

On the other hand, the density of circumferential fiber is appeared to be rather hard to control. However rather simple condition was experimentally found that ratio of the tension of the circumferential fiber to that of the radial fiber must be kept proportional to distance r. In the actual weaving process, the tension control and the addition of fiber bundle was made in the every N_f insertion. Due to difficulty of the continuous bundle addition, amplitude of the density variation in the shaped fabric was especially intensive when the fabric radius was small and it decreased with distance r. Although the variation of the fiber densities exists, the average of the variation in the shaped fabric was shown to be smaller than that in the shaped plane cloth especially when the fabric radius became large. Thus the shaped fabric is considered to be advantageous over the plane cloth. The same kind of fiber density control can be made for the tri-axial weave.

DEFORMATION OF SHAPED FABRIC COMPOSITE

Let us consider an antenna reflector as an application of shaped fabrics. As well known, the antenna reflector is required high dimensional stability to efficiently focus reflected electromagnetic waves. For optic reflector used in the space, especially high surface tolerance, say the order of μm , is sometimes required because the wave length of optical light is small and intensity of light is expected to be low in the space. Main reason to cause deformation of the reflector is two fold. They are due to external forces and variation of thermal environment. In the followings, we will solely deal with, the thermo-structural stability, namely deformation caused by the variation of temperature imaging the experience of the artificial satellites in the right and rear side of the earth.

It is obvious that material properties required mainly for the antenna reflector are low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and minimum variation of elastic moduli (EM)^{2),3)}. Thus let us first discuss CTE and EM of the shaped fabric composite (SFC) and the conventional plane cloth composite (PCC) when the shape of reflector is assumed to be a part of the sphericity. The analysis has been carried out on the basis of the following assumptions.

- (1) The orientations of fibers in SFC are directed to the longitude and latitude of the sphere (plane weave) and they are precisely kept in the composite.
- (2) The variation of properties in SFC is caused solely by the change of volume fraction of fibers V_f due to variation of fiber density shown in Fig.4.
- (3) Origin of the variation in PCC is the locational change of the intersection angle χ of fiber bundles as shown in Fig.3. This variation of χ causes variation of V_f as well as anisotropy of material properties.
- (4) V_f at the pole of the sphericity for the both of composites are assumed to be 50%.

The calculation was conducted using the formulation we previously presented for CTE and EM of 3-dimensional fabric composites^{6),7)}.

In Figs.7(a) and (b), the comparisons are made for CTE and Young's modulus of two kinds of the composites on the plane of $\phi=45^\circ$ where the variation of the properties in PCC is expected to be maximum. In the figures, θ and ψ denote longitudinal and latitudinal angles, respectively, as shown in Fig.4, the subscripts l and t denote properties in the direction of longitude and latitude of the sphere (see Fig.4), respectively, and the solid and dashed lines, respectively, stand for properties for PCC and SFC. It is obvious from the figures that, in SFC, the variation of EM is small and α is low. Thus SFC is advantageous over PCC especially when the considered part of the sphericity becomes deep.

Finally overall deformation for both of the spherical composites were calculated using commercially available FEM program, NASTRAN, and before-mentioned material properties EM and CTE. The root mean square RMS of displacement of the curved surface is nearly proportional to antenna efficiency. From the FEM calculus, RMS of the surface error by temperature change in SFC was shown to be superior to PCC.

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(a)

(b)

Fig.2 A spherical composite made of the shaped fabric of the plane weave (a) and the shaped tri-axial fabric (b).

Fig.3 Fiber orientation of the plane fabric (a) and shaped fabric (b).

Fig.5 Relation between deformation angle χ and longitudinal angle θ of various plane fabrics.

Fig.4 Definition of coordinate system.

Fig.6 Fiber density design of the circumferential fiber (a) and radial fiber (b).

Fig.7 Comparison of thermal expansion coefficients α_1 and α_t (a) and Young's moduli E_1 and E_t (b) between composites made of the shaped fabrics and plane fabrics.